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ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURA AS A PREDICTOR OF BURNOUT IN THE FLORICULTURE SECTOR OF PICHINCHA: IMPLICATIONS FOR WORKPLACE WELL-BEING AND ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The present study examines the relationship between organizational culture and burnout syndrome in the floriculture sector of Ecuador, a labor-intensive industry. The objective was to determine whether organizational culture is a key predictor of burnout, considering its impact on workplace well-being and organizational sustainability. A cross-sectional mixed design was employed, using a descriptive and correlational approach. Standardized instruments the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) and the Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) were applied to a sample of 183 employees from medium-sized floriculture companies. The results revealed a predominance of clan culture and high levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization among employees. However, no statistically significant relationship was found between organizational culture and burnout ($p = 0.104$). It is concluded that although clan culture is the most common in the sector, other factors may influence burnout, suggesting the need to explore additional variables to better understand and address workplace well-being in floriculture companies.

KEYWORDS: Organizational Culture, Burnout, Factor Analysis, Linear Regression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Burnout syndrome, according to (Leiter & Maslach, 2005) is a state of physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion caused by chronic workplace stress, which can have adverse effects on both employees health and well-being as well as overall organizational performance. It has currently become one of the main reasons for low labor productivity and job abandonment within organizations. In recent decades, the phenomenon of burnout has gained increasing relevance in the workplace, being recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a syndrome resulting from chronic work-related stress that has not been successfully managed. This syndrome is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced performance, affecting both workers' health and the sustainability of organizations (Organización Mundial de la Salud, 2019).

In Latin America, the prevalence of burnout has reached alarming levels. According to the Burnout 2024 study conducted by Bumeran, 91% of workers in Argentina, 89% in Chile, 88% in Panama, 78% in Ecuador, and 82% in Peru reported experiencing symptoms associated with this syndrome (Bumeran, 2023). In the Ecuadorian case, the trend shows a sustained increase: from 56% in 2020 to 74% in 2022, rising to 77% in 2023 and reaching 78% in 2024, which evidences an expanding problem in Ecuador (Bumeran, 2024). The most frequent burnout symptoms in Ecuador during 2024 include extreme exhaustion or lack of energy (43%), followed by negativism or cynicism toward work (32%), and a decrease in work effectiveness (19%).

Regarding associated organizational factors, work overload was identified as the main cause of burnout in Ecuador (25%), followed by mistreatment or negative relationships with hierarchical superiors (24%), pressure to meet job targets (16%), and lack of clarity regarding role and job responsibilities (17% combined). These factors are further aggravated by extended working hours, as nearly 59% of Ecuadorian workers reported working beyond the legally established 40-hour workweek, thereby increasing exposure to psychosocial risks. From an organizational perspective, the findings reveal that 9 out of 10 companies in Ecuador acknowledge the presence of burnout among their employees, representing a six-percentage-point increase compared to 2023. This finding reinforces the idea that burnout has ceased to be merely an individual experience and has become a structural organizational phenomenon, closely linked to management practices, leadership styles, and

prevailing cultural values within companies.

Taken together, these results highlight the direct influence of organizational culture on the emergence of burnout, especially in contexts characterized by high productivity demands, hierarchical leadership, and limited job autonomy. In this sense, burnout not only compromises workers' psychosocial well-being but also calls organizational sustainability into question by affecting productivity, engagement, and talent retention. These antecedents reinforce the relevance of analyzing organizational culture as a key predictor of burnout and as a strategic axis for promoting workplace well-being in labor-intensive sectors such as floriculture one of the pillars of the economy in Ecuador and highly demanding in terms of productivity and quality making it a suitable context for examining this relationship. Cameron & Quinn (2011) Organizational culture is defined as "a system of shared values that guide the actions and behaviors of an organization's members," which can either amplify or mitigate the causes of work-related fatigue or motivation. For example, a culture based on excessive competition among employees, poor communication, or a lack of balance between work and personal activities increases the risk that employees will experience burnout at some point. Conversely, an organizational culture that supports well-being, establishes clear roles, and promotes effective, motivational leadership can help reduce discomfort and strain among employees (Escobar, Deniz, Rivera, & Neri, 2022). Based on the above, the objective of this research is to determine the relationship between organizational culture and burnout syndrome in the floriculture sector, as well as its implications for workplace well-being and organizational sustainability.

1.2. Theoretical Foundation

Organizational culture is grounded in a robust theoretical framework that integrates the humanistic, behavioral, and organizational development approaches, all of which emphasize the central role of human behavior in workplace well-being. From the humanistic perspective, organizations are conceived as social systems in which well-being, human relationships, and emotional aspects directly influence employee behavior and job performance. Studies (Mayo, 1949) Hawthorne demonstrated that productivity does not depend solely on technical factors, but also on social integration, recognition, and attention to workers' psychological needs. Lewin explained this behavior through the balance between driving and restraining forces, highlighting the influence of the psychological environment on

cultural change processes. (Lewin, 1935). Meanwhile, Barnard (1938) included cooperation, legitimate authority, and communication as the cultural cement. Within the behavioral approach, Maslow (1943), McGregor (1960) and Herzberg (1959) explain how needs, managerial assumptions, and motivational/hygiene factors shape climates that either enable or mitigate exhaustion. Finally, organizational development integrates these contributions and directs them toward planned change, continuous learning, and the improvement of the work climate, promoting more adaptive, participatory, and sustainable cultures (French & Bell, 1984; Schein, 2010). Taken together, these approaches make it possible to understand how organizational culture can act as a key predictor of burnout.

Schein (2014) conceptualizes culture as a set of shared basic assumptions that guide the perceptions and behaviors of organizational members, represented at three levels: visible artifacts, espoused values, and underlying assumptions. Under this approach, a rigid culture can generate harmful practices and stress among workers. Authors, Deal and Kennedy (1982), propose the existence of four types of cultures: power, role, task, and person. They also argue that work focused on immediate results under rigid hierarchies deteriorates the organizational climate. Likewise, overly bureaucratic and results-centered cultures intensify work pressure. Along the same line, Cameron and Quinn identify four types of culture: clan, adhocracy, market, and hierarchy. Clan culture promotes teamwork and reduces the risk of job burnout, whereas market and hierarchical cultures characterized by excessive control and competitiveness increase the risk of emotional exhaustion among employees. (Cameron & Quinn, 1999). Theoretically, it can be observed that organizational culture can decisively influence the development or prevention of burnout. Highly competitive or market-oriented cultures, as well as rigid and inflexible leadership styles, can increase employees work-related exhaustion; conversely, more collaborative and supportive environments reduce the likelihood that employees will develop burnout.

Regarding burnout, two theoretical approaches have been identified: the psychological approach, which examines the interactions between individuals' personal characteristics and organizations that is, the mind-environment relationship and the behavioral approach, which focuses on how the work environment and past

experiences shape human behavior. From the psychological perspective, the contribution of Christina Maslach and Susan Jackson stands out; in 1981, they proposed the Three-Dimensional Theory of Burnout and defined it as a prolonged response to chronic emotional and occupational stressors, mainly produced by three factors: emotional exhaustion, described as physical and mental fatigue; depersonalization, related to detachment and isolation from others; and reduced personal accomplishment, expressed as low self-esteem and self-devaluation that lead to fear of facing job responsibilities due to perceived lack of competence or skills (Maslach & Jackson, The measurement of experienced burnout, 1981).

Arnold B. Bakker and Evangelia Demerouti, for their part, developed in 2007 the Job Demands Resources Theory, which examines how job characteristics affect mental health, job satisfaction, and work engagement. They concluded that when employees have sufficient resources, positive outcomes are strengthened, along with commitment, satisfaction, and performance. Conversely, when resources are insufficient, employees tend to experience exhaustion, stress, demotivation, emotional fatigue, and professional burnout. (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013).

In contrast, the behavioral approach seeks to analyze how the work environment and past experiences shape and condition human behavior. Thus, burnout is expressed as the result of the interrelationship between the demands inherent to work activities and the resources available to cope with them. When an imbalance arises between job demands related to effort level, time, and expectations and factors such as skills, social support, autonomy, and self-control in working life, burnout manifests. Within this line are theories such as the Demand-Control-Social Theory, developed by Robert Karasek and Jeffrey V. Johnson in 1986, and the Conservation of Resources Theory proposed by Stevan E. Hobfoll in 1998, which incorporates the idea that losses of gains or resources can behave like a spiral that generates increasing stress and exhaustion. (Pedrero, 2003).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents the studies that made it possible to understand the complex interaction between burnout and organizational culture, and how both factors can influence employees' well-being and performance.

In the healthcare sector Hsu et al. (2025), through a non experimental longitudinal design, examined

the influence of organizational culture on job burnout among medical and nursing professionals over time. It observed that organizational environments characterized by high workloads, limited resources, and the presence of role conflict show a sustained increase in burnout levels. The findings highlight that organizational culture directly affects workplace well-being; therefore, its proper management becomes a central element in preventing emotional exhaustion in the healthcare field.

In the study conducted by Nair *et al.* (2021) in several countries, they analyzed the relationship between organizational cultural values and levels of work-related stress across different national contexts. Using a comparative approach based on surveys and qualitative analyses, they found that organizational cultures oriented toward competitiveness, individualism, and constant performance pressure generate higher levels of stress among employees, unlike organizations with more balanced management practices, which show lower levels of work related tension. The authors conclude that organizational culture constitutes a determining factor in the experience of job stress and that cultural differences between countries significantly influence this relationship.

In the same line, Rosengrant (2018) in their case study conducted in the business sector, they analyzed how organizational values and practices influence the development of burnout. The results determined that organizational cultures focused on competition, achievement of results, and organizational success without adequate consideration for workers' well-being are associated with higher levels of emotional exhaustion. They conclude that organizational culture plays a key role in preventing burnout and that its management is essential for promoting healthier and more sustainable work environments.

Continuing with this same approach, Maslach y Leiter (2005) they analyzed the relationship between organizational values, management practices, and job burnout. Using a quantitative approach, the authors found that cultures characterized by high levels of competitiveness, low social support, and an imbalance between work and personal life show higher levels of burnout. In contrast, environments that promote support, fairness, and work-life balance are associated with lower emotional exhaustion. The study concludes that organizational culture is a determining factor in the experience of burnout and in employees well-being.

For their part, Mutah, Halasah y Qatawenah (2020), they investigated the relationship between

types of organizational culture and the dimensions of job burnout among administrative staff at Mutah University. Using a quantitative correlational approach, the study found that clan culture is positively associated with personal accomplishment, whereas market culture shows significant relationships with all dimensions of burnout. Likewise, hierarchical culture is mainly linked to emotional exhaustion. Consequently, the study confirms that different types of organizational culture influence employees' burnout experiences in distinct ways.

Within the context of small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in the province of Pichincha, García (2019) they investigated the relationship between leadership styles and organizational culture. Through a mixed exploratory, descriptive, and correlational approach, the findings show that transformational leadership is the most frequent style and is mainly associated with a clan-type organizational culture, characterized by teamwork and mutual support. The results indicate a significant, although moderate, influence of leadership on culture. Therefore, the study highlights the role of leadership as a relevant factor in shaping the organizational culture of the SMEs under study.

Focusing on the public sector, West y Dawson (2012), they analyzed how cultural differences among public entities influence employees' burnout levels. Through a comparative mixed-methods approach, the authors identified significant variations in leadership, internal communication, and staff participation, which directly affect workplace well-being. The results show that organizational environments with participative leadership styles and effective communication channels present lower levels of burnout. In conclusion, organizational culture constitutes a key factor in preventing burnout in the public sector.

In summary, the studies reviewed converge on a central idea: organizational culture deeply shapes people's work experiences and can become both a source of well-being and a trigger of burnout. Beyond the particularities of each sector – healthcare, private companies, public administration, or SMEs – the findings reveal a clear pattern: when organizations prioritize extreme competitiveness, constant pressure, and work without balance, employees experience higher levels of emotional exhaustion and stress. Conversely, environments that foster support, collaboration, open communication, and close leadership tend to protect individuals from burnout and strengthen their well-being. This convergence of evidence reminds us that culture is not an abstract or

decorative element, but a living factor that influences the daily health and motivation of those who are part of an organization. Therefore, managing culture with intention and sensitivity not only improves the work climate but also contributes to building more humane, sustainable organizations capable of caring for their people.

In this study, three hypotheses were proposed, which will be statistically tested later:

H1: The predominant culture in floriculture companies in the province of Pichincha is clan culture.

H2: The predominant burnout dimension in floriculture companies is emotional exhaustion.

H3: The relationship between organizational culture and burnout is strong, direct, and significant.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was structured under a mixed-methods approach, characterized by a set of processes for collecting, analyzing, and integrating quantitative and qualitative data. In the quantitative component, the standardized instruments Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) and Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) were applied. For the qualitative component, a documentary review technique was used through the examination of theoretical antecedents, previous studies, conceptual models, and reference frameworks; in addition, a focus group was conducted to complement the information obtained. The design was non-experimental and cross-sectional, analyzing the variables naturally within the organizational environment of floriculture companies in the province of Pichincha at a single point in time. The scope of the study was twofold: descriptive and correlational. In the descriptive aspect, the level and manifestation of burnout syndrome among employees of floriculture companies were characterized, as well as the predominant features of the organizational culture present in these companies. In the correlational aspect, the aim was to establish statistical associations between the study variables.

The population of interest for this study consisted of 6,264 employees who make up the workforce of medium-sized floriculture companies in the province of Pichincha. To calculate the sample size, a simple random probabilistic sampling method was applied with a 95% confidence level, resulting in a sample size of 362 individuals. However, due to the specific operational characteristics of the floriculture sector, 183 employees were available at the time of administering the two instruments, the MBI and the

OCAI, mainly because employees have limited availability during their work shifts to participate in additional activities.

In this context, the potential non-response bias was evaluated, considering that the obtained participation represents approximately 50.5% of the initially calculated sample. Despite this reduction, the number of cases collected allowed the planned statistical analyses to be carried out. Furthermore, the consistency of the linear regression model results ($R^2 = 0.121$; $p = 0.104$) and the fulfillment of its statistical assumptions indicate that the sample used is adequate for the analysis; therefore, no evidence of non-response bias that could compromise the validity of the study results was identified.

The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) is the gold standard instrument for assessing burnout syndrome worldwide, recognized for its strong psychometric robustness. An adapted version for organizational contexts was used, which allowed the measurement of the three core dimensions of burnout: 1) Emotional Exhaustion (EE), which evaluates the feeling of being emotionally and physically drained by work demands; 2) Depersonalization (DP), which measures the development of an impersonal, cynical, and detached attitude toward the recipients of one's work or toward colleagues; and 3) Reduced Personal Accomplishment (RPA), which reflects the tendency to evaluate one's job performance negatively and to perceive a decline in the sense of competence and achievement. The MBI items were answered using a Likert type scale, where participants indicated the frequency with which they experienced each statement, allowing for a precise quantification of burnout levels.

The second instrument used was the OCAI, developed and validated by Cameron and Quinn, recognized researchers in the field of organizational culture. This questionnaire makes it possible to diagnose the predominant current culture as well as the desired culture, considering six key dimensions: 1) Dominant characteristics, which refer to the distinctive and prevailing traits of organizational culture, such as orientation toward innovation, stability, or the market; 2) Organizational leadership, which evaluates how leadership is exercised within the organization, including aspects such as leadership style, decision-making, and communication; 3) Organizational climate, which analyzes how human resources are managed, including staff development, motivation, and performance management; 4) Cohesion factors, which focus on the mechanisms that unite organizational members, such as shared values, team

cohesion, and sense of belonging; 5) Management style, which evaluates the organization's strategic objectives and priorities, as well as the alignment of actions with those objectives; and (6) Criteria of success, which refer to the standards and criteria used to assess performance and success within the organization (Cameron & Quinn, 2006). Employees were required to rate each statement on a scale from 1 to 100, distributing a total of 100 points among the four options included in each dimension. (Cameron & Quinn, 2006).

Since both instruments are widely used in the academic field, they were subjected to quantitative validation through a pilot test involving 50 participants. The results of this validation yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.912 for the MBI and 0.904 for the OCAI, respectively values considered excellent thus confirming the reliability of the instruments. Data collection was carried out using the Google Forms platform, and processing was conducted with the statistical software SPSS v.27. For the analysis of the burnout variable, the statistical technique of exploratory factor analysis was used, which made it possible to identify the underlying dimensions that make up work-related stress in the floriculture sector. Regarding organizational culture, the methodology proposed by Cameron and Quinn was applied; and to determine the relationship between the two variables, linear regression analysis was performed.

4. RESULTS

This section presents a detailed analysis of the results obtained through the OCAI and MBI instruments, with the objective of identifying the dominant organizational culture and the predominant symptom among employees of floriculture companies in the province of Pichincha, as well as the results regarding the relationship between the study variables.

4.1. Typology of Organizational Culture in Floriculture Companies

4.1.1. Cultural Orientation

Using the methodology proposed by Cameron and Quinn, scores were obtained for each type of organizational culture within the companies under study. Figure 1 illustrates the current culture in floriculture companies in the province of Pichincha.

Figure 1: Current Culture.

Note. The figure represents the current organizational culture as perceived by employees of the companies.

The predominant culture is clan, accounting for 38.54%, which suggests that employees feel part of a large family and that the organization prioritizes the well-being and development of its members—an essential factor for fostering a harmonious and productive work environment. The lower presence of adhocratic culture, representing 14.73% of the total, indicates a limited inclination toward innovation, creativity, and flexibility, highlighting an opportunity for improvement in the search for new market segments, dynamism, and adaptability within a competitive environment such as the flower export industry. The balance between hierarchical culture (23.38%) and market culture (23.33%) shows that companies value both stability and control, as well as competitiveness, goal achievement, and results orientation. Overall, these results indicate that although the sector values a collaborative and stable work environment, it could benefit from greater attention to innovation and adaptability.

4.2. Cultural strength

It is determined based on the number of points assigned to a specific type of culture (Cameron & Quinn, 2006). Figure 2 shows the cultural strength of the floriculture companies, graphically represented on a Cartesian plane with red points. The concentration of these points in a specific quadrant indicates the predominant cultural strength.

Figure 2: Cultural Strenght.

Note. The figure shows the cultural strength of the employees in the companies.

In Figure 2, it can be observed that with 118 points, clan culture predominates, indicating that a large number of employees value a collaborative and community-oriented work environment. In contrast, adhocratic culture received only 3 points, reflecting a limited representation of values such as innovation, creativity, flexibility, and adaptability in a constantly changing global market.

For this variable, the following hypothesis was proposed: H1. The predominant culture in floriculture companies in the province of Pichincha is clan culture. Based on the results presented in this section, the hypothesis is accepted.

Burnout Symptoms in Floriculture Companies

To identify the symptoms of burnout within the companies under study, the technique of exploratory factor analysis was used, which according to (Thompson, 2004), helps uncover the dimensionality of the observed variables and identify possible correlations among them without imposing a preconceived structure. To determine the suitability of the data for this method, adequacy tests were conducted. The KMO index was 0.835, which, according to evaluation criteria from the literature, is considered excellent. Additionally, Bartlett’s test of sphericity was significant (p = 0.000) with a statistic of 241.404. These results confirm the existence of correlations among the variables and justify the application of the factor analysis model .

Additionally, a single component explains

63.791% of the total accumulated variance in the dataset. The high proportion of explained variance suggests that this component has considerable capacity to summarize the underlying structure of the original data, facilitating the understanding and interpretation of the relationships among the observed variables. Based on these tests, the component matrix was constructed, showing the factor loadings of each variable on the extracted factor. Table 1 identifies the most relevant factors for burnout symptoms.

Table 1: Components matrix.

Dimensions of Burnout	Component 1
Emotional Exhaustion	0,954
Depersonalization	0,937
Personal Accomplishment	-0,353

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis
a. 1 Extracted Components.

Note. The table shows the component matrix with its respective factor loadings

The burnout variable is strongly associated with emotional exhaustion (0.954) and depersonalization (0.937), while it shows a low or inverse relationship with personal accomplishment (-0.353). This latter result may be explained by the fact that 89.60% of the participants have only a basic or high school level of education, which could influence a lower perception of the need for personal and professional fulfillment. First, employees in floriculture companies experience a depletion and loss of emotional resources, reflected in a feeling of being emotionally overwhelmed and exhausted by work. Second, employees show

cynicism or disengagement as a response to the exhaustion experienced on the job, tending to mentally distance themselves from work and adopt an insensitive or indifferent attitude toward their responsibilities, colleagues, and clients. Third, personal accomplishment or, conversely, personal inefficacy indicates that employees perceive themselves as unable to meet established work standards, linked to a decline in their sense of competence and success in job performance.

For the burnout variable, the following hypothesis was proposed.: H2: The predominant burnout dimension in floriculture companies is emotional exhaustion. Based on the above, this hypothesis is accepted, since the predominant dimension is emotional exhaustion, with a value of 0.954.

Burnout Level in Floriculture Companies

The following section aims to assess the frequency and intensity levels of burnout through its dimensions, each of which has a specific scale with three categories (low, medium, high) indicating signs of burnout. This information is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Reference Values for Measuring Burnout Levels.

	Low	Medium	High	Signs of Burnout
Emotional Exhaustion	0-18	19-26	27-54	More than 26
Depersonalization	0-5	6-9	10-30	More than 9
Personal Accomplishment	0-33	34-39	40-56	Under 34

Note. The table shows the reference values for measuring the level of burnout. Adapted from Maslach & Jackson (1996). Maslach Burnout Inventory Manual (3rd ed.). Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.

Using the methodology proposed by Maslach and Jackson in the MBI, burnout indicators were calculated by dimension, and through a visual traffic-light technique, the levels were represented: red for high burnout, yellow for medium, and green for low. The results obtained are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Signs of Burnout.

	Level	Average	Signs of Burnout
Emotional Exhaustion	High	39.6	More than 26
Depersonalization	High	18.6	More than 9
Personal Accomplishment	Medium	38.43	Under 34

Note. The table shows the values indicating signs of burnout for each dimension.

According to the MBI reference values in Table 3,

emotional exhaustion and depersonalization reach high levels, reflecting clear signs of burnout among employees. In contrast, personal accomplishment is at a medium level, indicating some perception of achievement and competence, though with room for improvement.

Continuing with the analysis, Figure 3 shows the level of burnout for each of its dimensions.

Nota. The figure displays the percentage of each

burnout dimension at high, medium, and low levels

The figure shows that 84% of employees experience high emotional exhaustion, indicating a state of persistent fatigue and mental burnout that may be related to the intensive demands of their work. This can result in reduced productivity, increased absenteeism, staff turnover, and lower product quality, the 85% of employees, mostly operational staff, experience high levels of depersonalization, reflecting a significant emotional detachment from their work and colleagues. This distancing may be a consequence of the intensive and repetitive nature of the tasks, affecting not only product quality but also team cohesion and collaboration. The repercussions include decreased commitment and motivation, potential increases in internal conflicts, and deterioration of organizational culture, the 38% of employees feel highly accomplished in their work; this indicator may negatively impact their motivation and overall job performance.

Organizational Culture as a Predictor of Burnout in Floriculture Companies

The purpose of this section is to determine whether the study variables are related, for which the statistical technique of linear regression was used. Before applying this technique, the statistical assumptions were verified. First, the normality of the residuals was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, yielding a significance value of $p = 0.200$ ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the residuals have a normal distribution. Second, to check for homoscedasticity, the Breusch-Pagan test was applied, yielding $p = 0.318$ ($p > 0.05$), demonstrating that the variance of the errors is constant. Finally, the assumption of independence of the errors was assessed using the Durbin-Watson statistic = 1.89, a value within the acceptable range (1.5–2.5), indicating the absence of autocorrelation. Having met these assumptions, the regression was applied, and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation of Study Variables.

Burnout and Organizational Culture		
Coefficient of Determination	R^2	.121
ANOVA	Sig.	.104

Note. The table shows the relationship identified using the linear regression technique, with burnout as the endogenous variable and organizational culture as the exogenous variable.

Since the p-value is 0.104, which is greater than 0.05, this result indicates that the correlation is not statistically significant. Therefore, the results suggest that there is no relationship between organizational culture and burnout. This information is crucial for the floriculture sector, as it highlights the importance of exploring other factors that may be affecting employee well-being.

The following hypothesis was proposed: H3: The relationship between organizational culture and burnout is strong, direct, and significant. Based on the data obtained in this section, hypothesis H3 is rejected; therefore, no association between the study variables can be confirmed.

Additionally, it was explored whether the cultural dimensions (clan, hierarchical, and market) individually predict symptoms of burnout. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Relationship between Organizational Culture Types and Burnout Dimensions.

Type of Culture	Linear Regression Analysis	Emotional Exhaustion	Depersonalization	Personal Accomplishment
Clan	Coefficient of determination	.115	.153	.216
	Sig.	.121	.039	.003
Adhocratic	Coefficient of determination	.158	.066	.064
	Sig.	.032	.378	.391
Market	Coefficient of determination	.092	.082	.152
	Sig.	.214	.270	.040
Hierarchical	Coefficient of determination	.190	.181	.190
	Sig.	.010	.014	.010

Note. The table shows the relationship identified through the linear regression technique, where the Burnout dimensions represent the endogenous variable and the type of Organizational Culture represent the exogenous variable.

The table shows that for Adhocratic, Market, and Hierarchical cultures, there is no accepted significance value; therefore, they do not show a relationship with the Burnout dimensions. In contrast, for Clan culture, although the correlation is weak, the fact that it is statistically significant (.003) indicates that the characteristics of this culture are, to some extent, influencing employees' Personal Accomplishment.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of this study reveal interesting findings regarding organizational culture and burnout in the floriculture sector of Pichincha. The prevalence of clan culture (38.54%) suggests a strong focus on teamwork, employee development, and a supportive environment. This finding aligns with previous studies (Mutah, Halasah, & Qatawenah, 2020; García, 2019), which highlight the benefits of this type of culture for employee well-being. In a labor-intensive sector like floriculture, where tasks are often repetitive and demanding, a collaborative environment can mitigate stress and foster greater engagement. However, it is important to note that clan culture is not a panacea. If not balanced with other elements, such as innovation and efficiency, it may lead to complacency and a lack of adaptability. The low presence of adhocratic culture (14.73%) in this study could indicate this limitation.

The confirmation that emotional exhaustion is the most prevalent dimension of burnout (0.954) reinforces the idea that the floriculture sector imposes high emotional demands on its workers. This result aligns with research highlighting the relationship between workload, lack of control, and emotional exhaustion (Hsu *et al.*, 2025; Maslach y Leiter, 2005). In the specific context of floriculture companies, factors such as pressure to meet quality standards, irregular work schedules, and exposure to challenging environmental conditions may contribute to employees' emotional fatigue. It is crucial to address this issue through intervention strategies that promote work-life balance, social support, and the development of stress coping skills.

The lack of a statistically significant relationship between organizational culture and burnout ($p = 0.104$) is the most surprising and challenging finding of this study. Contrary to the initial hypothesis and other studies that have documented a significant influence of culture on burnout (Rosengrant, 2018; West y Dawson, 2012), The results suggest that, in the context analyzed, organizational culture does not act as a direct predictor of burnout syndrome. One possible explanation lies in the specific characteristics of the floriculture sector, where factors such as working conditions, the physical demands of the job, pressure to meet production targets, and the operational nature of the tasks may have a more immediate impact on workers' well-being than organizational cultural values.

Furthermore, the literature suggests that organizational culture may influence burnout indirectly through mediating variables such as leadership, organizational climate, or perceived

organizational support. In this sense, it is possible that the relationship between organizational culture and burnout in the present study is mediated by other organizational factors that were not included in the analyzed model.

Finally, it should be noted that the significance value obtained ($p = 0.104$) is relatively close to the conventional threshold of statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that future research could further explore this relationship, particularly by analyzing the different dimensions of organizational culture individually.

Despite the absence of a direct relationship between culture and burnout, the high levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization observed have important implications for employee well-being and the sustainability of floriculture companies. Regarding well-being, physical health problems such as chronic fatigue, headaches, gastrointestinal disorders, and cardiovascular issues may arise. Mentally, symptoms of anxiety, depression, irritability, difficulty concentrating and making decisions, and even sleep disorders can develop. These conditions increase absenteeism and staff turnover, as employees seek less demanding jobs or companies that offer a better work environment and development opportunities (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). According to the Job Demands Resources theory, this situation leads to decreased job satisfaction, resulting in lower motivation, commitment, productivity, and professional growth when resources are insufficient (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013). Overall, burnout not only affects the workplace but also extends to personal life, causing family, social, and relational problems.

Regarding the sustainability of companies, the consequences of burnout such as lack of concentration, frequent errors in tasks, a negative work environment, lack of collaboration, and cynicism (Maslach & Jackson, 1981) have serious implications. These directly affect productivity, work quality, organizational reputation, and competitiveness, generating economic losses due to additional costs borne by the organizations. In conclusion, the findings highlight the need for interventions that promote work-life balance while strengthening control and social support (Johnson & Hall, 1988), as well as the development of coping skills to halt the spiral of resource loss and mitigate stress (Hobfoll, 1998).

From this study, several lines of research emerge aimed at deepening the understanding of organizational culture and burnout in the floriculture sector. First, it is pertinent to analyze: ¿what other contextual factors—such as working conditions, leadership styles, and individual characteristics— affect this phenomenon beyond organizational culture? Similarly, it is worth exploring: are there significant differences in burnout levels according to the type of company, considering variables such as size, location, or productive specialization? In the same way, it would be relevant to examine: what is the mediating role of variables such as social support, job demands, and leadership in mitigating the effects

of a highly competitive organizational culture? Furthermore, there is a need to compare the floriculture sector with other economic sectors to identify differences in burnout levels and cultural dynamics, as well as the factors that explain them. Finally, it is suggested to adopt a longitudinal perspective that allows observing the evolution of organizational culture and burnout over time, and to incorporate performance indicators that enable the evaluation of their impact on business results.

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